

A New Paradigm For Environmental Data Management Technology

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Data is an overused term that encompasses virtually every dimension of our modern daily lives. Because that data is so abstract in concept, the exploitation of said data can reach a level that it is quite difficult for us to grasp. Almost all of our personal and professional data is processed, stored, and reprocessed in a private and obscure infrastructure without us realizing it.

The ubiquity of data comes associated with the idea and practices collectively known as Data Extractivism [1]. This paradigm stipulates that everything is a data source that can and should be economically exploited, and that nothing should interfere with this commodification process. Data extractivism is so intrinsic to modern economic systems that much of the data thus extracted from our digital interaction is meaningless outside the exploitative logic. Its severity has already brought about regulatory measures such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [2]. Although quite limited in trying to reign in the abuses of the massive industry of data exploitation, the regulation does, if nothing else, expose the obscene excesses of data collection and processing in the first place. This profitable amount of data can also be the target of surveillance organizations [3,4] that find in it a fertile place to "mine" valuable information to monitor society and use it as a way of coercion, or regulatory action.

In 2013 Edward Snowden revealed the massive surveillance apparatus built up by the US National Security Agency (NSA), often in partnership with the big technological corporations (Facebook, Google, Microsoft, Apple, etc...) that provide their infrastructure [4,5]. In 2017, the scandal involving Cambridge Analytica and Facebook brought to light even more clearly how the control of our data by Big Tech is dangerous by adding biases in an election, indicating a wider threat to democracy.

This data economy is not strictly technological, but also (or firstly) a social and political issue, demanding from us deep reflection about the implications of data exploitation. We live in a world with thousands of people living under extreme social vulnerabilities, and with researchers developing relevant studies on ecology and climate change but threatened with censorship.

Openness, Ethics and Environmental Data

Privacy by design is one of the key principles safeguarding human dignity. However, the fetishisms of openness and transparency oversimplify the natural world and minimize the associated risks. Users holding such data have the right to decide whether they want to share it or not. I support open environmental data since it emphasizes the collective benefits foremost, and diminishes the authority of control, among other ethical issues. The availability of certain information can open up a person or group to risk, benefiting economic interests at the former's detriment. This is a social and political issue, and there is a constant trade-off between its technological and the social aspects. These aspects are not inseparable and, once they are attempted to be separated, the result is a lack of ethical principles.

Nevertheless, we need more comprehensive, higher-quality data on natural ecosystems concerned with conservation and environmental research. For instance, ensuring high-resolution information on freshwater flows and water levels along with the dynamics of freshwater species, making use of *in situ* and remote sensing technologies is as important as it is under-served. Additionally, modeling studies are also needed to

support the design of conservation and restoration alternatives by identifying potential trade-offs and synergies among land management, water resources, climate, and biodiversity outcomes, among other issues.

As we can see broadly documented, there is availability of sensitive environmental data such as geo-located information of exotic species [6] and resource exploitation that intensify habitat disturbance, species extinctions, or create other negative impacts. In some cases, data openness benefits people or companies in positions of power [7], instead of the intended beneficiaries of the data sharing, for example, data that provides private corporations with information on mineral resources or pure water that they can exploit. Additionally, the early publication of specific data when a community is actively seeking to demonstrate river contamination due to agricultural run-off can lead to a Strategic Lawsuit Against Public Participation (SLAPP) or Lawfare [8,9].

The previous examples don't encourage us to rely on available services for our privacy and security. From password leakage to censorship, there are many public examples. To name a few; since 2011, the Dropbox service had at least 11 big security issues [10]. In 2019 Github, now Microsoft's affiliate, started blocking or removing repositories after governmental complaints [11,12].

Moreover, the most popular data storage services used today are not developed for openness or justice and don't provide users with clear information about governance and data ownership. This judicial insecurity provides a fertile field for private profit, at the detriment of scientific and social advances.

The privacy and security concerns have become mainstream, as well as the impact of academic works intersecting with social aspects [13]. The NSA mass surveillance scandal [4,14], and the task force coordinated by climate scientists and hackers to protect climate data from Trump and other climate denialist threats [15], make clear that we should think about privacy and security applied also to environmental data. This is the next frontier of greed around data extractivism.

Environmental data sovereignty has been central to my activities since the second part of my Ph.D. studies. With Hacking Ecology, I have started to consolidate this idea using a systemic approach, covering both hardware and software data systems. In the last four years, the big question that guides us has been: “How could new tools bring environmental data protection to another level?”. The reflection around this took us outside the omnipresent, foggy, and distracting world of Silicon Valley: the wonderland raising billions of dollars exploiting our data without any commitment to ethics or collective benefits.

Where We Are Going

We know that just understanding the risks and rejecting the pact with Big Tech are not enough. We need accessible, secure and user-friendly alternatives that can also challenge the current business model. Those in which human dignity, equity, sustainability, and social development are the foundational principles.

Since 2019 we have been working on the hardware side of things. After having tested the sensors, we integrated them to build our open multi-parameter aquatic probe focused on environmental research and participatory science. But data management for open source hardware used to be just the implementation of complementary technology without intent to be a real alternative to the current infrastructure. For us, it was clear that palliative measures are not enough, and we should work to provide users with a new and ambitious approach to environmental data.

Currently, most of the available frameworks based on decentralized architecture are only effective for distributing non-controversial public data, as they don't provide protection of metadata that can identify users and the organizations working on sensitive topics. This lack of data protection in particular is a relevant issue for environmental data [16] since we understand that many times environmental datasets and studies are subject to multiple conflicts of interest. Thus, our first step was to define a framework for a privacy and security-preserving system. The system would provide users with:

- Total control over their data
- Persistence of data
- Resistance against adversaries (data leak, censorship, legal coercion, etc.)
- Data minimization
- Geo-privacy
- Version control
- Append-only data management
- Data replication in a distributed system

These principles are the very foundation, but we must go beyond them and achieve a systemic approach integrating the necessary tools for environmental monitoring, data management, and extensible features to connect to other tools and accommodate changes. They must address:

- End-to-End Encryption (E2EE)
- Real-time data compatibility
- Repository for group work
- Data veracity mechanisms
- Data licensing tool (such as Creative Commons and open data license)
- Right to decide over one's data
- Integration with data analysis tools (e.g., R, Python, Matlab, gnuplot, etc.)

- Set of open algorithms that will provide users with forecasts and predictive models

To this end, we have started by inviting researchers, community scientists and programmers to be active contributors to the process of development. Soon we are going to work together implementation and system improvements. The objective is a complete shift of power relations, breaking the excessive concentration of power in the hands of the few massive corporations controlling environmental data, as well as providing legal frameworks to protect the environmental and personal data from misuse, aligned to the needs of citizens.

We are at a tipping point of the data sovereignty debate. With the environmental crisis reaching unprecedented levels, we must know who controls and who uses environmental data. Big Tech is trying to maintain and extend the old and abusive structures, no matter the cost. On the other side, groups like Hacking Ecology are breaking with this logic and proposing a more inclusive and empowering paradigm in which society is in the center.

The best solution is people deciding over data using transparent infrastructure that ensure security and privacy in an accessible way. And we are already doing this together. You can follow our next updates, and please let us know if you can contribute to the project.

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